

Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and activities - Initial

D5.1a

CiROCCO

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

Consortium

1	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS)
2	Ethniko Asteroskopeio Athinon (NOA)
3	eBOS Technologies Limited (EBOS)
4	Netcompany-Intrasoft SA (INTRA)
5	InoSens doo Novi Sad (INO)
6	Astrocast SA (ASTRO)
7	Centre for Environment and Development for the Arab Region and Europe (CEDARE)
8	University of Cyprus (UCY)
9	Idalion Municipality (DIMOS)
10	Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance (MOL)
11	Public Enterprise “Vojvodinašume” Petrovaradin (VSUME)
12	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)

Dissemination level	Public (PU)
Type of deliverable	R – Document, report
Work package	WP5 – Impact Maximisation and Outreach
Deliverable number, title	D5.1a Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and activities - Initial
Status - version, date	V0.5, 19/09/2023
Deliverable leader	ICCS
Contributing partners	INO, EBOS, NOA
Contractual date of delivery	n/a
Keywords	Dissemination, communication, exploitation plan

Quality Control

	Name	Organization	Date
Peer review 1	Petros Mouzourides	UCY	20.09.2023
Peer review 2	Panayiotis Harbas	DIMOS	21.09.2023

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Organization	Summary of changes
ToC	12/07/2023	Katerina Erato Zouroufidou	ICCS	
v.01	19/07/2023	Eleni Athanasopoulou, Marios Sophocleous	NOA, EBOS	Input (webinars, blogposts, newsletter) Input (website)
v.02	20/07/2023	Katerina Erato Zouroufidou	ICCS	Incorporation of input
v.03	01/08/2023 06/09/2023	Jelena Dokic	INO	Input (exploitation plan)
v.04	07/09/2023	Katerina Erato Zouroufidou	ICCS	Incorporation of input
v.05	20/09/2023	Petros Mouzourides	UCY	Review
v.06	21/09/2023	Panayiotis Harbas	DIMOS	Review
Final Draft	22/09/2023	Katerina Erato Zouroufidou	ICCS	Incorporation of comments

Legal Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. The information in this document is provided “as is”, and no guarantee or warranty is given that it is fit for any specific purpose. The CiROCCO project Consortium members shall have no liability for damages of any kind including without limitation direct, special, indirect, or consequential damages that may result from the use of these materials subject to any liability which is mandatory due to applicable law.

Copyright © CiROCCO Consortium, 2023.

Table of contents

Consortium	2
Quality Control.....	3
Version History	3
Legal Disclaimer	3
List of Figures	7
List of Tables	7
List of Abbreviations and Acronyms	9
Executive Summary.....	10
1. Introduction.....	11
1.1. Project Introduction	11
1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable.....	11
1.3. Intended Audience	11
1.4. Deliverable Structure.....	11
1.5. Relation with Other Work Packages and Deliverables.....	12
2. Communication and Dissemination Plan	13
2.1. Approach	13
2.2. Communication and Dissemination Goals	13
2.3. Key Audiences	14
2.4. Key Messages	15
2.4.1. General Messages	15
2.4.2. Key Words	15
2.4.3. Tailored Key Messages	15
3. Project Identity and Templates	17
3.1. Project Identity	17
3.1.1. Logo.....	17
3.1.2. Colour Palette.....	18
3.1.3. Brand Book	18
3.2. Templates	18
4. Communication Tools and Actions	19

4.1.	Online Tools.....	19
4.1.1.	CiROCCO WEBSITE.....	19
4.1.1.1.	Methodology for website construction and development.....	19
4.1.1.2.	Website content and screenshots.....	20
4.1.1.3.	Google Analytics Website Traffic.....	22
4.1.2.	CiROCCO Blog.....	22
4.1.3.	CiROCCO Social Media.....	23
4.1.3.1.	LinkedIn.....	23
4.1.3.2.	Twitter.....	24
4.1.3.3.	YouTube/Vimeo.....	25
4.1.4.	CiROCCO Podcast.....	25
4.2.	Dissemination and Communication Material.....	26
4.2.1.	Brochure, Poster, Roll up Banner (ICCS).....	26
4.2.2.	Newsletter.....	28
	29
	29
4.3.	Press activities.....	29
4.3.1.	Local information spreading.....	29
4.4.	Conferences and Events.....	30
4.5.	Publications.....	30
4.6.	Educational activities.....	30
4.6.1.	Webinars.....	30
4.6.2.	Workshops.....	32
4.7.	Networking and liaison activities.....	33
4.8.	Source Code Repository.....	34
4.9.	Q&A Platform.....	35
5.	Implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan.....	35
5.1.	Partner's roles.....	35
5.2.	Roadmap.....	36
5.3.	Dissemination Procedure.....	39
5.3.1.	EU Acknowledgment.....	39
5.3.2.	Monitoring and recording.....	41
6.	Exploitation Plan.....	42
6.1.	Exploitation strategy.....	42
6.2.	Joint Exploitation strategy.....	44
6.3.	Key Exploitable Results.....	45
6.4.	Individual Exploitation Plans.....	48
6.4.1.	Research Institutes and academic organisations.....	49
6.4.2.	Industrial Organisations and Small Medium Enterprises.....	53

6.4.3. Public Organisations.....	56
7. Strategy for the Management of Intellectual Property	59
8. Conclusion.....	59
9. References	60
Annexes	61

List of Figures

Figure 1: CiROCCO logo, colour negative	17
Figure 2: CiROCCO logo, colour	17
Figure 3: Colour Palette.....	18
Figure 4: CiROCCO Website - Smartphone View	20
Figure 5: CiROCCO Website Structure.....	20
Figure 6: CiROCCO Website – Home Page.....	21
Figure 7: Google Analytics.....	22
Figure 8: CiROCCO LinkedIn Page.....	24
Figure 9: CiROCCO Twitter Page.....	25
Figure 10: CiROCCO Rollup banner	26
Figure 11: CiROCCO brochure	27
Figure 12: Screenshot of Newsletter #1.....	28
Figure 13: Mailchimp Analytics	29
Figure 14: EU Acknowledgment	39
Figure 15: EU Acknowledgment Example	40
Figure 16: CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline.....	45
Figure 17: CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline.....	45
Figure 18: Deliverable Template	61
Figure 19: Ppt Template	61
Figure 20: Individual Communication and Dissemination plans	62
Figure 21: Dissemination Procedures.....	63
Figure 22: Activity Report.....	64
Figure 23: Calendar of Events.....	65
Figure 24: Dissemination Registry.....	65
Figure 25: List of Conferences	66
Figure 26: List of Publications.....	67
Figure 27: Individual Exploitation Plan.....	68

List of Tables

Table 1: Key Audiences.....	14
Table 2: Key Messages per Target Audience.....	15
Table 3: Initial Blog Post Plan	23
Table 4: Initial Plan-Webinars	31
Table 5: Initial Plan-Workshops.....	33

Table 6: WP5 Partner PMs	35
Table 7: Roadmap.....	36
Table 8: Monitoring and Recording.....	41
Table 9: Exploitation summary for datasets created during CiROCCO	46
Table 10: Summary of dissemination material efforts by partners	48

List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
T	Task
GEO	Group on Earth Observations
GEOS	Global Earth Observing System
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
EC	European Commission
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
TBD	To be Determined
TBA	To be Announced

Executive Summary

This deliverable is the principal result of Task T5.1. It provides a comprehensive outline of the communication and dissemination approach devised for the CiROCCO project, including the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan to be implemented within the project. The primary purpose of this plan is to ensure substantial engagement with essential stakeholders and audiences throughout the project duration. The document includes the following:

- The dissemination, communication and exploitation objectives of the CiROCCO project.
- The roles and responsibilities of the partners regarding communication and dissemination activities.
- The main targeted audiences.
- The dissemination tools and communication channels that will be used by the consortium partners to maximize visibility and public awareness. These include promotional material, social media, websites, newsletters, project-organized events, external events with partner participation, scientific and non-scientific publications, as well as synergies with similar projects and initiatives, and sister projects.
- The reporting templates for communication and dissemination activities, which partners will complete throughout the project, encompassing event reporting, templates for participation in external events/conferences, and the overall dissemination reporting template.
- The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for monitoring and evaluating the dissemination activities implemented under CiROCCO's communication and dissemination efforts.
- The exploitation activities which will be used to the effect of commercially exploiting the project's end products.

All partners are expected to actively participate and contribute to the implementation of the dissemination activities, following the dissemination and communication strategy. ICCS will closely monitor the dissemination actions described in this document and provide necessary support. It will additionally deliver two further reports, D5.1 "Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan and activities, interim report" and D5.2 "Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation plan and activities, final report".

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Introduction

CiROCCO aims to address the vulnerability of desert ecosystems to climate change. These unforeseen changes can disrupt the delicate balance of desert ecosystems, affecting nutrient cycles, fire patterns, and water distribution. Furthermore, climate change in desert areas can have far-reaching effects, including the transport of dust storms and pollutants over long distances. This is particularly evident in the Mediterranean Basin, where desert dust outbreaks from North Africa contribute to air pollution.

Due to the lack of ground-based observational networks in remote areas like deserts, satellite-derived data is commonly used to estimate meteorological parameters. However, these datasets often have significant biases, making it challenging to calibrate numerical models accurately. CiROCCO will establish an end-to-end sensing system that combines cost-effective sensing nodes, advanced data fusion remote sensing techniques, and assimilation modeling. This network of sensors will improve ground observations in desert areas, providing an operational and easily maintainable solution. The project also emphasizes the commercialization of services to ensure the sustainability of the installation. Additionally, the project aims to support the integration and assimilation of data within the Cross-COPERNICUS ecosystem, promoting the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) management of data.

1.2. Purpose of the Deliverable

This document provides an overview of the plans for the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities that are scheduled for the duration of the project. It includes the CiROCCO communication, dissemination, and exploitation objectives, identifies the target groups to address and the respective channels and tools to be used in order to effectively reach them and achieve awareness.

Since communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, require team effort, it is of major importance for all partners to be familiar with all opportunities and the procedures to be followed, so this document aims to serve as a guideline providing key information.

1.3. Intended Audience

This document is intended for the CiROCCO Consortium partners, the European Commission (the funding authority), and other individuals or groups interested in obtaining further information about the project. As a publicly accessible deliverable, it will be available at the CiROCCO website after receiving approval from the European Commission.

1.4. Deliverable Structure

Deliverable D5.1a, titled "Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plan and activities" consists of seven chapters. In the first chapter, the CiROCCO project is introduced, providing an overview of the deliverable's scope, its intended audience, its relationship to other WP deliverables and tasks, and the definition of key concepts. The second chapter outlines the dissemination and communication approach and objectives, including the targeted audiences and key messages. Chapter three focuses on the project's identity and templates, while chapter four presents the planned tools, channels, and success criteria for evaluating dissemination activities within the CiROCCO project on an annual basis.

Chapter five presents a preliminary action plan, providing insights into the dissemination procedures employed within CiROCCO. Furthermore, KPIs agreed upon in the General Assembly are presented. Chapter six briefly refers to the exploitation plan to be followed by the consortium partners and finally, the seventh chapter concludes the document.

1.5. Relation with Other Work Packages and Deliverables

The deliverable D5.1a, titled 'Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation plans and activities,' serves as the primary output of task T5.1. It is closely connected to tasks T5.2 'Capacity Building, Trainings and Policy Outreach on Hard-to-reach Areas', T5.3 'Coherent Business Model(s), Exploitation Activities and Market-entry Preparation Plan' which will develop the appropriate business models for the exploitation procedures and T5.4 'Collaboration with sister projects. Additionally, it is closely associated with the following project deliverables:

- i. D5.1: The Interim report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation, which covers all dissemination, communication, and standardization activities carried out during the first eighteen months of the project, along with the planned activities.
- ii. D5.2: The Final report on dissemination, communication, and exploitation, which documents all dissemination, communication, and standardization activities conducted during the second half of the project's duration. It also provides a summary of the most significant achievements in dissemination, communication, and standardization throughout the project's lifetime.

Apart from the aforementioned tasks and deliverables, this document indirectly relates to all the project's accomplishments that require dissemination and communication.

Outside of WP5, D5.1a is related to WP2 and more specifically T2.1 "Stakeholder Mapping and End-user Needs Analysis through Processes of Co-creation", which will map target groups and stakeholders. It is also related to WP4 "Pilots for Improved Geographical Coverage and Impact Assessment", and in particular Tasks 4.2-4.5 which are the four pilots in Egypt, Cyprus, Serbia and Spain, targeting different geographical locations, features and governance services. D5.1a will serve as the initial plan upon which further communication and dissemination activities will be added and will serve as a guide to the consortium and partners assigned with spreading news and information to the local communities where the pilots will be performed.

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1. Approach

CiROCCO will use a network of sensors to monitor the environment in desert areas. It provides four core services, including renewable energy planning, air quality monitoring, ecosystem management, and emissions modeling. The project will test its capabilities in real-world conditions in four countries and commercialization services will ensure the sustainability of the facility. From this information the conclusion which is drawn is that this project touches all aspects of everyday life, from the political to the environmental and is also aiming towards producing exploitable results.

The main objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy are to create a brand for the project, to set up a plan for activities which will help the project achieve its targets, to clearly define the stakeholders to which the activities will be communicated and to define the messages and channels through which they will be communicated. This process is crucial to successfully disseminate the scientific knowledge produced during the project as well as the benefits which this project will bring to everyday lives of the general public.

Additionally, the successful implementation of the dissemination and communication plan is imperative to secure the exploitability of the final product and to draw light to its commercial aspect.

The specific approach followed by CiROCCO is Laswell's model of communication¹ which is comprised of five elements:

This model is chosen because it gives us a linear pathway to set our communication goals through first coming up with our key messages that we want to communicate, then deciding which communication channels are going to be used and subsequently identifying out audiences and matching them to the communication channels and messages we have come up with. This process is done to result in the final step, which is to create an effect on the receiver of the message. The effect can either be the acquisition of knowledge, the change of an attitude or the facilitation of a behavior.

2.2. Communication and Dissemination Goals

In order to create a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy, firstly there have to be clear goals set and then there need to be relevant activities designed to achieve these goals. As set out in the project's grant agreement, the high-level objectives for all communication and dissemination activities are summarized as follows:

¹ <https://helpfulprofessor.com/laswell-model-of-communication/>

- To provide a clear understanding of the vision and objectives of the project as well as the anticipated positive impact it will have on the life of European citizens;
- To determine the most suitable channels and methods for communicating the progress and outcomes of the project to both identified stakeholders and the general public;
- To establish strong collaborative ties and exchange knowledge with relevant EU-funded projects, fostering cooperation and synergy;
- To disseminate scientific findings of CiROCCO and gather valuable feedback from other researchers and pertinent expert communities interested in the relevant subject matter.

By addressing these goals, CiROCCO aims to develop a comprehensive Dissemination and Communication strategy that effectively promotes its objectives and achievements to a wide range of target audiences.

2.3. Key Audiences

Identifying key audiences and matching the most effective communication channels and messages to them is extremely important in ensuring that the potential effect of the message is reached. In the table below (Table 1), key audiences are grouped together and matched to the most effective communication channels.

Table 1: Key Audiences

Communication Channel	Key Audience					
	Decision makers & Public Authorities	ICT SMEs, industries, investors	Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives	Environmental agencies and hubs	General Public, civil society	Local audiences (pilot areas)
Website		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Social Media		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Newsletter		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Blogs			✓	✓	✓	
Scientific publications			✓	✓		
Videos/Presentations in events	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Podcasts	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Dissemination Material	✓	✓	✓	✓		
Press activities	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Workshops/Webinars	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

2.4. Key Messages

Key messages are an integral part of every dissemination and communication strategy and form the basis upon which targeted key messages can be build. They can be used by the partners to present the actions and outcomes of the project in a consistent way, according to the project brand.

2.4.1. General Messages

CiROCCO's vision is to establish a novel system of sensing nodes in hard-to-reach desert areas with the aim to better evaluate desert dust products. This will establish the added value of the new sensing systems which can provide a low-cost alternative in testing model developments and assimilation procedures with abundant and reliable data sources.

2.4.2. Key Words

In this section are identified the key words describing the project's concept:

- Monitoring air quality
- Putting desert research in focus
- Improve quality of life for those living close to desert areas
- Lowering the manufacturing cost of in-situ sensing nodes
- Knowledge exchange

2.4.3. Tailored Key Messages

The following table shows key messages and the target audience they correspond with.

Table 2: Key Messages per Target Audience

Target Audiences	Key Message
1. Decision-makers & Public Authorities 2. General public, civil society 3. Local audiences	CiROCCO helps proactive policy making to protect from the environmental, health and socioeconomic challenges of dust in the atmosphere

<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public authorities 2. ICT SMEs, industry, investors 3. Academia, innovations actors, relevant initiatives 4. Environmental agencies and hubs 	<p>CiROCCO has direct impact towards the Green Deal – Zero pollution priorities</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public authorities 2. ICT SMEs, industry, investors 3. Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives 4. Environmental agencies and hubs 	<p>CiROCCO develops intelligent & low-cost sensing systems and networks for environmental monitoring</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public authorities 2. Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives 	<p>CiROCCO establishes dedicated hubs on atmospheric dust effects, facilitating collaboration, knowledge sharing and coordinating efforts among environmental agencies</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public Authorities 2. General public, civil society 3. Local audiences 4. Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives 5. Environmental agencies and hubs 6. ICT SMEs, industry, investors 	<p>CiROCCO strengthens EU and international science-policy interfaces to achieve Sustainable Development Goals</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public authorities 2. General public, civil society 3. Local audiences 4. Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives 	<p>CiROCCO develops decision-support technologies for environmental monitoring</p>
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Decision-makers & Public Authorities 2. Local audiences 3. Academia, innovation actors, relevant initiatives 4. Environmental agencies and hubs 5. ICT SMEs, industry, investors 	<p>CiROCCO will aid in the understanding of trends and patterns in desert and dust related challenges</p>

3. Project Identity and Templates

3.1. Project Identity

The brand identity of a project is one of the most important aspects of its Communication and Dissemination plan and with that in mind CiROCCO has set out to create a strong visual identity which will be applied throughout the project. The visual identity is made up of the project's logo, a dedicated colour palette, a brand book and the respective document templates are uploaded to the CiROCCO online repository and are available to the consortium.

3.1.1. Logo

For the logo, a modern and clean look that conveys the project's vision of innovation and sustainability is suitable. A color palette of earth tones was used to represent the desert environment and innovation. The logo is simple and recognizable, with strong and clear typography that emphasizes the name of the project. The graphics style uses geometric shapes and minimalist design, with a focus on data visualization. The spherical, orange coloured shape of the "O" creates a clear connection with the Sun, which is inextricably linked with desert environments and creates a further reference to solar power and sustainability. At the same time, the curved lines linking the different elements elude the transfer of data and information.

Figure 2: CiROCCO logo, colour negative

Figure 1: CiROCCO logo, colour

3.1.2. Colour Palette

The colours that were selected for the project logo were inspired by the desert and arid terrains where the pilots will be run. These colours will be used consistently throughout the project in order to ensure a cohesive brand identity and increase the project's recognizability.

CiROCCO		COLOUR GUIDE	
MAIN COLOURS			
CiR	CCO		BLACK # 000000 R 0 G 0 B 0 C 0 M 0 Y 0 K 100
	ORANGE to BROWN Gradient	Orange # ff8e2c R 255 G 142 B 44 C 0 M 55 Y 100 K 0 Brown # 7d2e00 R 126 G 45 B 0 C 30 M 85 Y 100 K 38	
	ORANGE	Orange # ff8e2c R 255 G 142 B 44 C 0 M 55 Y 100 K 0	
BROWN BACKGROUND COLOUR			
			2 Brown # 593029 R 89 G 48 B 41 C 43 M 75 Y 73 K 50

Figure 3: Colour Palette

A number of secondary colours have also been selected and those can be viewed in the CiROCCO brand book below.

3.1.3. Brand Book

In order to help the partners, use the project logo properly, adhere to the colour guide and know the brand typography, a CiROCCO brand book was created. The brand book ensures identity cohesion throughout different communication channels and dissemination material and is available to the consortium on the CiROCCO repository and to the wider public via our [website](#).

3.2. Templates

In order to ensure a consistent look when conducting either internal or external events, a number of templates have been created for the CiROCCO project, using MS office. This set of templates is made up of:

TEMPLATES

- A power point template
- A word template for Deliverables
- A general presentation of the project

Partners have access to the above templates through the CiROCCO repository. In this document they are presented in [Annex 1](#).

4. Communication Tools and Actions

4.1. Online Tools

4.1.1. CiROCCO WEBSITE

The CiROCCO website has been created to function as the public face of the project. This website employs cutting-edge technology to deliver information-rich content to its visitors. The CiROCCO website constitutes a component of the project's dissemination efforts. To access the Project website, please utilize the following internet address: <https://CiROCCO-project.eu/>.

4.1.1.1. Methodology for website construction and development

In developing CiROCCO's official website, careful attention has been given to incorporating user interface design principles and ensuring a positive user experience. The website features a modern interface that utilizes state-of-the-art technology to ensure compatibility across multiple browsers and devices. Moreover, the CiROCCO interface is fully responsive, user-friendly, and facilitates a seamless user experience by providing content-rich information to visitors. This means that users can access the CiROCCO website from smartphones, tablets, desktop PCs, or laptops and easily navigate through the content. The design and implementation processes both prioritize a user-centered approach, aiming to create an efficient and user-friendly interface.

During the implementation of the CiROCCO interface, the technologies of HTML5², CSS3³, and JavaScript⁴ were utilized to achieve a responsive design that ensures compatibility across various browsers and devices. To provide a visual representation, **Error! Reference source not found.** showcases the appearance of the website when accessed on a smartphone.

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/2017/REC-html52-20171214/>

³ https://www.tutorialspoint.com/css/css3_tutorial.htm

⁴ <https://www.javascript.com/>

Figure 4: CiROCCO Website - Smartphone View

4.1.1.2. Website content and screenshots

The website structure of CiROCCO was developed using a mapping tool known as SlickPlan⁵. Figure 4 illustrates the sitemap of the initial working version of the CiROCCO website in the form of a diagram.

The “Home” page of CiROCCO website is the one loaded first when the user enters the CiROCCO website in a web browser.

The screenshot shows the CiROCCO website home page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the CiROCCO logo on the left, and links for Home, About, Dissemination & Communication, and News & Events. On the right of the navigation bar, there is a 'Contact Us' button and social media icons for LinkedIn and Twitter. The main content area features a large background image of a desert landscape with a network of lines overlaid, suggesting a sensing system. The headline reads 'Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts'. Below this, there is a dark brown box titled 'CiROCCO's vision' containing a paragraph of text and a 'Read More' button. Further down, there is a section titled 'Key Objectives' with five numbered items (01-05) describing the project's goals. A 'Manage consent' button is visible in the bottom right corner of the page.

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

CiROCCO's vision

CiROCCO's vision is to establish an end-to-end sensing system, composed of a distributed network of cost-effective sensing nodes coupled with state-of-the-art data fusion remote sensing and assimilation modelling techniques. The defined network of sensors will enhance the current lack of ground observation in desert areas offering an operational and in parallel easy-to-maintain-and-expand solution. Commercialisation services will ensure the installation's sustainability and simultaneously the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) management of data will support Cross-COPEMNICUS ecosystem integration and assimilation services.

[Read More](#)

Key Objectives

- 01 Install and operate in-situ, low-cost, stand-alone, electronic sensing nodes in close collaboration with post-project operating entities, having a real interest from local communities, including the commercial sector, offering a clear sustainability and commercialisation path beyond the project's duration.
- 02 Establish a low-cost and sustainable network of electronic sensing nodes in under-sampled desert areas and ecosystems in Egypt, Serbia and Spain.
- 03 To develop data processing services based upon ICT infrastructure that allows to gain access to data from hard-to-reach, under-sampled areas, and further improve their quality by data fusion services.
- 04 Provide data for the research community, aiming to enhance climate change models and further support the research for the European Green Deal challenges; this includes the development of better dust particle movement models and increase the understanding of dust movement towards the European territory, as well as providing Renewable Energy S Planning and Ecosystem Management services.
- 05 Cross-COPEMNICUS ecosystem integration and assimilation.

[Manage consent](#)

Figure 6: CiROCCO Website – Home Page

The "Home" page showcases a relevant background image related to the Project, capturing its essence. Additionally, a central button is provided to encourage visitors to access more detailed information. Below these elements, the "Home" page incorporates distinct links, designed appropriately, that guide users to various dissemination and communication activities. It also includes an option for subscribing to the Project newsletter and provides information about the Consortium. Upon loading the website

for the first time, users are presented with an "Accept Cookies" option, allowing them to customize their preferences at any given time. The Terms of Service and Privacy Policy are in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and are publicly accessible via the following URLs, which can be reached from the "Home" page.

<https://cirocco-project.eu/cookies-policy/>

<https://cirocco-project.eu/privacy-policy/>

4.1.1.3. Google Analytics Website Traffic

Google Analytics⁶ is a cost-free web analytics service provided by Google, utilized to monitor website traffic and generate reports based on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). The CiROCCO website is registered with Google Analytics, which offers a comprehensive range of reports to satisfy even the most demanding webmasters. Figure 7 below presents a sample screenshot depicting the analytics results generated for the period between March 1, 2023, and July 12, 2023, providing an overview of the audience information, including:

- Number of sessions, users, and page views.
- Average session duration and the percentage of new sessions.
- Demographic statistics, such as sessions per country.
- Breakdown of users accessing the webpage from different devices (desktop and mobile).
- Real-time active users and user engagement data by the time of day, among other metrics.

Figure 7: Google Analytics

4.1.2. CiROCCO Blog

Apart from the scientific publications in established peer-reviewed journals, CiROCCO aims to connect with the broad public, through a periodic promotion of activities in popularized journals/blogs, open communities/organizations and other communication channels. The 15 (or more) virtual presences of CiROCCO in this particular category of online media (at 8 or more different blogs/channels) will be distributed in the whole duration of the project, the short-term (less in number) disseminating the concept and planning, the long-term (more in number) advertising/describing the results of the project, focusing on the 4 pilot applications. Apart from the English articles, blog contributions in the local native language/National blogs of the involved countries are also planned. **Error! Reference**

source not found. shows the proposed plan for the communication activity using the specific means. This is a dynamic planning, references the minimum provisions. Adjustments are expected, which will be presented in the following versions of this deliverable.

Table 3: Initial Blog Post Plan

Communication channel	Potential Theme	Partners	Number of posts
Horizon Magazine/blog	Addressing the climate change effects in desert areas: the vision the outputs	ICCS	2
Copernicus News/blog	Exploitation of and/or contribution to Copernicus	TBD	x
Kosmos (NOA's popularized) magazine	Overview of CiROCCO and the Greek contribution Dust Cycle and Interactions: Representation in Models Dust Cycle and Interactions: Assimilation with Observations Project results and perspectives	NOA	4
GEO blog	Capacity development In situ monitoring in unrepresented areas Project results promoting GEO	NOA	3
PARSEC Accelerator Insights	Solar energy planning and management	NOA & CEDARE	1
Ecotec (Greek environmental blog)	Novel environmental technologies	NOA	1
Spanish blog	TBD	CSIC	1
Serbian blog	TBD	VSUME	1
Cyprus blog	TBD	UCY, DEMOS	1
Egypt blog	TBD	CEDARE	1
...			
Total: >8 blogs			>15 articles

4.1.3. CiROCCO Social Media

CiROCCO will build and maintain actively its online presence in several social media channels, using Twitter and LinkedIn when interacting with research and innovation communities spreading out new publications, while podcasts and video streaming platforms will be used for wide community engagement.

4.1.3.1. LinkedIn

When looking to reach professionals, LinkedIn is the go-to social platform. Through the LinkedIn profile

CiROCCO EU Project, CiROCCO aims to reach a broad spectrum of audiences, some of which are scientists, policy makers, research institutes and businesses in industries relevant to its research, and also connect with other relevant projects and engage in dialogue and information exchange. Since the page was launched in M2, the project’s LinkedIn page has attracted 44 followers.

Figure 8: CiROCCO LinkedIn Page

4.1.3.2. Twitter

Twitter is another social media platform used by CiROCCO, where under the account name [@CiROCCO_eu](#) account the project’s news can be disseminated in real-time in a direct and engaging manner. The account is also used to connect with relevant projects and initiatives, EU institutions and EU officials and to make CiROCCO part of conversations in its related fields.

Since the page was launched in M2, the project’s LinkedIn page has attracted 30 followers.

Figure 9: CiROCCO Twitter Page

4.1.3.3. YouTube/Vimeo

During the project, at least four videos will be created and disseminated to the public through YouTube and Vimeo. The project will produce multimedia material to have a self-explanatory and appealing presentation of the project, leveraging available distribution channels of promotion (e.g., YouTube, Vimeo). Also, a set of video interviews, both from scientific partners, to collect inputs, taking advantage of plenary meetings and events of relevance will be implemented in close collaboration with the CiROCCO capacity building activities. These account channels will be set once the material is ready to be uploaded.

4.1.4. CiROCCO Podcast

CiROCCO will take advantage of the momentum that podcasts have currently and create two cycles of 4 episodes each. The episodes will be comprised of interviews where our researchers and developers will talk about their work, as well as interviews with environmental actors who will explain the importance of in-situ monitoring in desert areas and the impact that dust particles in the atmosphere have on the climate, local animal species and the health of humans. Podcasts will help the project reach a younger demographic and to penetrate different conversation spaces than with more traditional media.

Impact

- Societal**
Increase decision-making capacity for future missions and climate change priorities by providing data from unrepresented areas. Direct impact towards the Green Deal - Zero pollution priorities.
- Environmental**
Increase the precision of developed models by 10% and offer dedicated services to tackle climate change adaptation and mitigation planning.
- Economic**
A cross-sectoral business models are developed aiming to showcase the sustainability of the developed system. A decrease of 60% of the total price per monitoring station is expected.
- Scientific**
Findings are made available to the community for further research. Follow-up actions are planned for the sustainability of the system. >70% of CiROCCO stations to join global environmental monitoring networks by fully respecting their standards.
- Capacity building**
Training of local stakeholder groups aiming to cultivate the necessary skills to operate the network in the long run.

4 Pilots

Pilot 1 Egypt

Given its geographical location, by far the most important potential source of renewable energy for Egypt is the sun.

- Impact of dust on solar radiation and energy production.
- Upgrades and additional installations of sensing nodes.

Pilot 2 Cyprus

The island of Cyprus is affected by frequent and sometimes severe Desert Dust Storm (DDS) events.

- Evaluate DDS event predictions.
- Assess the accuracy of the Sand and Dust Storm Warning Advisory and Assessment System (SDS-WAS) models.
- Study impact of DDS events on Municipality of Idalion.
- Early warning dissemination system for DDS events.

Pilot 3 Serbia

Largest inland sandy terrain in Europe - home to rare and endangered plant and animal species. Prone to strong winds carrying pollutants from nearby thermal plants.

- Assist in decision-making processes such as reforestation, planning measures, monitoring microclimate and air pollution.

Pilot 4 Spain

One of the most extensive badland landscapes in semi-arid, south-east Spain and one of the driest areas in Europe.

- Measure environmental variables to understand aerosol particle exchanges.
- Evaluate the performance of operational models for predicting DDS events.
- Study the differences in air quality and ecosystem services.
- Establish an early warning system for DDS events.

A strong foundation - the system architecture

- Seamlessly integrate in situ observations from low-cost and high-end stand-alone sensing nodes deployed in hard-to-reach areas together with remote sensing data compiled from satellite and ground observations.
- Support the fusion between remote sensing and in-situ data as well as the development of calibration models and assimilation methodologies to capture the variability of targeted solar radiation, air quality and other environmental parameters.
- Ingest and handle massive amounts of data into pipelines for both real-time and batch processing - independent of whether these are observations or data from simulations.
- Streamhandler orchestrates the information flow by providing all the necessary technologies and components that enable storage, processing, analysis and distribution of the data in a fault-tolerant and secure manner.
- Scalable ecosystem for sharing data with GEOSS, Copernicus and other ESA services.

CiROCCO's Vision

CiROCCO's vision is to establish a novel system of sensing nodes in hard to reach desert areas with the aim to better evaluate desert dust products. This will establish the added value of the new sensors, which can provide a low-cost alternative in testing model developments and assimilation procedures with abundant and reliable data sources.

Outputs

- Renewable Energy Systems planning.
- Air quality early-warning system for human health.
- Land use and ecosystem management.
- Modelling of Green House Gases and particles emissions, to validate the quality of the collected data and drive the sustainability and exploitation path of the overall system.

Partners

Objectives

- Install and operate in-situ, low-cost, stand-alone, electronic sensing nodes with post-project commercialisation in mind.
- Establish networks in under-sampled desert areas and ecosystems.
- Develop data processing services based upon ICT infrastructure.
- Provide research data to enhance climate change models and further support research.
- Cross-COPERNICUS ecosystem integration and assimilation.
- Accelerate the adoption of the CiROCCO tools and services by the wider community.

Project Facts

Call: HORIZON-CL6-2023-GOVERNANCE-01

Topic: New technologies for acquiring in-situ observation datasets to address climate change effects

Duration: 36M (2023-2026)

Start Date: 01 March 2023

Sustainable investing goes mainstream

As organisations become obligated to report on ESG indicators, monitoring data becomes key for assessing environmental impacts of business activities, providing quantitative impacts. Derived information brings value to investors, regulators and general public as well, ensuring a more transparent and trustworthy measure that helps differentiate real impacts from 'greenwashing'. To the benefit of the citizens, CiROCCO novel sensor monitoring data will be used to track air pollution and help monitor deforestation and biodiversity. Using a combination of EO and GNSS supports the use of smart energy grids, helps companies plan operations of energy generation so as to optimise their performance and monitor key infrastructure and optimise maintenance. Overall, CiROCCO solutions contribute to compliance, monitoring and efficiency of green investments fostering sustainable practices.

Enhancing the In-situ Environmental Observations across Under-sampled Deserts

Figure 11: CiROCCO brochure

27

4.2.2. Newsletter

A quarterly digital newsletter in English is planned to be produced during CiROCCO's lifetime. The newsletters will provide information about the project, its progress and outcomes, the vision and the innovative solutions provided, participation in conferences, news and events, or other relevant material. The newsletters are supported by the Mailchimp campaign software, and are aligned to the aesthetic of the website, following the colour guide and media included (images, videos). The newsletter team keeps track of news and events between issues to create informative content about the project which will be addressed to research and technology stakeholders, local communities involved in the pilots, decision and policy makers/authorities and EO service providers. Achievements of partners and the involvement of CiROCCO in events will also be included. The newsletters are sent via e-mail. The recipients' list will be dynamically populated, through the subscription form in the project's website, which will be systematically and repeatedly disseminated to the wider community of CiROCCO, its sister projects, as well as other projects that CiROCCO's partnership is involved in. In addition, the newsletters are uploaded on the website ([here](#)) and advertised through the social media of the project (e.g. [here](#)).

The newsletter provides an effective way to disseminate the project to interested stakeholders, keep them updated and informed, summarize the added value provided and the efforts done from the previous issue, while automatically keeping track of analytics of Open & Click rate and Reads.

In July 2023, [Issue #1](#) was distributed. This newsletter's purpose was to disseminate project information, news and events among stakeholders, sharing the vision and the innovative solutions provided. A sample of the analytics (1/77/'23) is provided below.

Figure 12: Screenshot of Newsletter #1

72 Recipients

Audience: CiROCCO Subscriber List

Delivered: Mon, Jul 30, 2023 9:30 AM

Subject: Introducing CiROCCO: Revolutionizing Desert Observation

[View email](#) · [Download](#) · [Print](#) · [Share](#)

37 Opened	3 Clicked	0 Bounced	0 Unsubscribed
--------------	--------------	--------------	-------------------

Successful deliveries	72 100.0%	Clicks per unique opens	8.1%
Total opens	90	Total clicks	3
Last opened	7/17/23 3:50AM	Last clicked	7/10/23 9:21AM
Forwarded	0	Abuse reports	0

Figure 13: Mailchimp Analytics

4.3. Press activities

Leveraging online publishing platforms and magazines will enable CiROCCO to reach out to a broader audience. Also, all partners will disclose non-confidential information of the project in their national language to local/regional newspapers, media and press, and the impact of the demonstrated pilots will be promoted. According to the GA signed between the parties, before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the granting authority. Therefore, whenever a communication activity that is expected to reach the general public (not the specialized press or media) like an interview with the coordinator for national TV, an article in a national newspaper, etc., is scheduled, the project coordinator will inform the Project Officer.

ICCS, as the Dissemination, Communication and Liaison activities task leader, will disseminate press releases upon the project's milestones and share them with the consortium to be further disseminated through each partner's media network. Such an example is the press release written for the project's Kick off Meeting, which took place in March 2023. All press releases are available on the consortium repository and CiROCCO's [website](#).

4.3.1. Local information spreading

In addition to the general press releases that will be addressed to the wider European and international audiences, localized press activities will take place. In the spreading and citizen engagement in pilot countries, leaders will be CEDARE, UCY+DIMOS+MOL, VSUME and CSIC, as they hold better knowledge of the local media landscape.

More specifically, these press releases will communicate information relating to the pilots as well as the workshops that will take place in the pilot countries.

4.4. Conferences and Events

As part of its dissemination activities, CiROCCO will participate in scientific conferences and events with the aim to raise awareness and share information. A list of conferences and events that are relevant to CiROCCO's field of research has been compiled and is available on the CiROCCO repository and also shown in [Annex 4](#). This list will be continuously updated throughout the project.

There are two milestone events scheduled for the duration of CiROCCO and both are organized by ICCS. These are the Project Kick off Meeting, which took place in Athens in March 2023, and the final event, which will conclude the project and is scheduled for M36.

4.5. Publications

CiROCCO will strongly focus on publishing its research in peer-reviewed scientific and technical journals and presenting it in relevant conferences. A list of journals has been created and shared on the CiROCCO repository to aid the consortium in their efforts, and it is also shown in [Annex 5](#). This list will be continuously updated throughout the project.

In an effort to make research findings widely available, CiROCCO partners are encouraged to use Open Research Europe, the new open access publishing platform for the publication of research stemming from Horizon Europe funding, as well as the Zenodo platform.

Zenodo is an Open Science research repository provided by CERN and in alignment with the European Commission's vision to facilitate the open access and open data movements in the EU. A [CiROCCO community](#) has been created on the platform and all partners will be encouraged to share their research in it.

4.6. Educational activities

CiROCCO will perform a number of educational activities, namely webinars and workshops. More specifically, ICCS will organise the workshops (virtual and physical), whereas NOA and UCY will organize webinars, as a means of knowledge transfer, wider outreach and sustainability. These activities will follow an iterative sequence through which stakeholders advance in the process towards improving geographical coverage of in-situ environmental observations, with focus on hard-to-reach and under-sampled areas across Europe and beyond.

A tentative plan of the webinars and workshops is presented in the following paragraphs.

4.6.1. Webinars

A number of webinars (>10) will be organized and used as a means of knowledge transfer, sustainability and wider outreach. For the first two purposes, the audience will be targeted and mainly derived from the stakeholder list composed in the frame of T2.1. These webinars are planned for the long-term, once the developed solutions in the 4 pilot areas have matured and even farther, after the implementation of pilots. Important components of the presentation material will be to explain to end-users, the role and the placement of all innovations, as well as provide a comprehensive and

trusted framework that strictly defines the data operations, in addition to the benefits that such a system can deliver to its end beneficiaries.

Wider webinars targeting a broad audience, will promote the wider project in all participating countries and across EU. European Networks (e.g. ICLEI Europe) will be reached in order to inform interested local governments in the planned/provided project solutions. Webinars targeting the GEO community which deals with desert areas at the global scale (e.g. Africa deserts) will also be organized, because of the similar challenges with respect to the adoption of in situ EO infrastructure, thus the exploitation of the experience to be gained from the capacity development in the pilot areas of the project.

The following is a dynamic plan which references the minimum number of events. Adjustments are expected, which will be presented in the following versions of this deliverable. Supporting material (background, templates) is currently in preparation. All webinars will be recorded and publicly available through the official website of the project.

Table 4: Initial Plan-Webinars

No. Of Webinars	Subject	Target Audience	Organiser	Comments	Timeframe
2	planned/provided project solutions	local governments of Europe	NOA	Co-organization with ICLEI Europe	M12/M32
1	Lessons learnt from capacity development in the pilot areas	GEO community	NOA	Co-organization with GEO CD coordinator	M34
2	The adoption of in situ EO infrastructure in remote areas	GEO community	ICCS	Co-organization with sister projects and in collaboration with GEO in situ subgroup	TBA
1	Solar Energy Planning and Management in Egypt	Local community Egypt	CEDARE	Co-organization with NREA	TBA
1	Solution for Pilot 2	Local community Cyprus	UCY		TBA

1	Solution for Pilot 3	Local community Serbia	VSUME		TBA
1	Solution for Pilot 4	Local community Spain	CSIC		TBA
1	Enhancing Dust Understanding: Synergistic Utilization of Models and Observations	Dust modeling community	NOA		M30
Total: > 10					

4.6.2. Workshops

A number of at least 8 workshops will be organized by ICCS during the duration of the project. The workshops will take place in different phases of the project, and more specifically different phases of the pilots. This is important, since the stakeholders that will be engaged in the workshops (the stakeholders are identified through T2.1) will provide the consortium with valuable feedback. The importance of the results from these workshops is twofold.

Firstly, in the initial phase of pilot preparations the stakeholders will provide the partners who are building the pilots with feedback which will assist them in improving their operations and resolve the obstacles that they will have encountered.

Secondly, in the later stage of the project which is marked with the completion of the pilot systems. The workshops can provide the consortium with invaluable insight into how to exploit the project's results and strengthen its commercialization approach.

Additionally, these workshops can serve as discussion roundtables where partners and stakeholders can discuss policy making approaches, exchange best practices, share exploitation tactics and overall create and sustain a partnership that will make up the network needed for CiROCCO's Networking and Liaison activities (T5.4) which is further talked about in the next chapter.

All workshops will adapt a hybrid model in order to maximize participation and engagement.

The following table presents an initial plan for the workshops that will be conducted. This plan is of course dynamic and subject to changes according to the progression of the technical aspects of the pilots.

Table 5: Initial Plan-Workshops

Subject	Organization	Location	Timeframe
Cyprus Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Initial pilot phase.	ICCS-UCY-DIMOS-IDALION-MOL	Cyprus (physical and virtual)	M8
Egypt Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Initial pilot phase.	ICCS-CEDARE	Egypt (physical and virtual)	M9-M10
Serbia Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Initial pilot phase.	ICCS-VSUME-INO	Serbia (physical and virtual)	M11-M12
Spain Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Initial pilot phase.	ICCS-CSIC	Spain (physical and virtual)	M13-M14
Cyprus Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Demo in real life conditions.	ICCS-UCY-DIMOS-IDALION-MOL	Cyprus (physical and virtual)	M16
Egypt Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Demo in real life conditions.	ICCS-CEDARE	Egypt (physical and virtual)	M19
Serbia Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Demo in real life conditions.	ICCS-VSUME-INO	Serbia (physical and virtual)	M22
Spain Pilot -Stakeholder engagement and feedback. Demo in real life conditions.	ICCS-CSIC	Spain (physical and virtual)	M27
Final event workshop	ICCS-Pilot Leaders	tba	M36

4.7. Networking and liaison activities

The project will collaborate with the other projects funded under HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-07 and potentially with other running projects dealing with relevant and pertinent subjects in order to exchange best practices, implement synergies where possible and deliver added value communication, dissemination and exploitation activities towards all stakeholders, including EU policy makers and scientific communities. In addition, our project will develop a comprehensive set of activities to network and cluster with other relevant projects. To this purpose, the following activities will be undertaken:

- Networking meetings with the Project Boards and project partners of the projects on a regular base.
- Networking meetings with the Project Boards of the international related projects identified as relevant for collaboration.

- Discussion round tables with the above-mentioned Project Boards and project partners with other relevant national and international actors and, in particular, members of the technology platforms, scientific organisations and operational groups set up by the EC in which the project partners are already involved. In addition, the project will provide comprehensive Reports once/twice a year on the conclusions extracted from the clustering activities mentioned, as well as a short version of the Reports for non-scientific end users. The project will also implement effective stakeholder engagement activities to approach other EU and international projects, platforms/clusters/PPP Associations, with complementary technologies and/or strategies.

The CiROCCO consortium has already strong cooperation with ongoing relevant partnerships, networks and bodies, including Copernicus In-situ Component and Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service through ICCS, GEO-CRADLE, GEO-VENER, Urban Heritage Climate Observatory, GEO In-situ subgroup, GEOSS Infrastructure Development Team and Climate Change Working Group through NOA, DAIRO, AIOTI, NGI and NESSI through EBOS, and EMODnet through CSIC.

ICCS is the T5.4 leader and has already identified the sister projects funded under HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-07. These are:

- EUROPEAN LIDAR ARRAY FOR ATMOSPHERIC CLIMATE MONITORING - EULIAA
- Autonomous Multi-Format In-Situ Observation Platform for Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide and Methane Monitoring in Permafrost & Wetlands - MISO
- A SYstem for reaL-time obserVation of Aeroallergens - SYLVA
- Transformative Environmental Monitoring to Boost Observations in Africa - TEMBO Africa
- Unmanned Airborne Water Observing System - UAWOS

A remote networking meeting with TEMBO Africa was conducted on the 20th of July where the two projects presented a short PowerPoint Presentations and the intention to collaborate was established.

Furthermore, CiROCCO has expressed its intention to participate in the Horizon Results Booster program in the same project group as MISO, for which an invitation was received on July 21st.

4.8. Source Code Repository

Encouraging a transparent and open-source culture, CiROCCO will make accessible its software repositories through well-known distributed source code platforms. Well-established repositories to be used: GitHub and Bitbucket.

4.9. Q&A Platform

Conversations about the project repository would be concentrated in reference sites. The selected Q&A platform will be the Stack Overflow, the largest, most trusted online community for developers to learn and share knowledge.

5. Implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

5.1. Partner's roles

While all partners are expected to contribute to the communication and dissemination activities through either performing individual communication tasks (website, blogs, newsletter etc.), and dissemination activities (publishing in scientific journals, participating in conferences, conducting workshops and webinars etc.), ICCS as the Task5.1 leader is assigned with monitoring all such activities for the CiROCCO project. To that end ICCS has asked all partners to provide a plan for their communication and dissemination activities through filling out an individual “communication and dissemination plans and activities” form, which can be found in [Annex 2](#).

Table 6: WP5 Partner PMs

Partner	PMs in WP5
ICCS	12
NOA	10
EBOS	6
INTRA	3
INO	26
CEDARE	4
UCY	4
DIMOS	4
MOL	4
VSUME	4
CSIC	5
ASTRO	3

5.2. Roadmap

A Dissemination and Communication roadmap and preliminary action plan have been created, which outline the channels and tools that will be used to reach target audiences, as well activity related actions that will be taken in order to reach the project's KPIs as they have been specified in the GA.

Table 7: Roadmap

Phase 1 M1-M12			
Description	Communication Activities	Actions in relation activities	Milestones & Deliverables
In the first phase of the project the main focus will be on creating a strong brand identity, relevant communication material and creating a comprehensive list of journals, event and conferences.	Design of logo, definition of colour palette, creation of brand-book and templates (Brand identity)	Ready prior to KoM	D5.1a Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan and activities.
	Communication material	Rollup banner-Ready at the KoM Four-fold brochure M5	
	Website	Launched M1 Unique visitors by M12 >1,200	
	Social Media (LinkedIn+Twitter)	Launched M2 Size of online community >400 Impressions/month >100	
	General Spreading	>3 Press Release	
	e-Newsletter	1 st Newsletter sent M5 Quarterly Issues	
	Presentations in conferences and events	>4	

	Joint activities with sister/relevant projects	Link with >5 projects >6 initiatives >5 events >8 fairs	
	Workshops and Webinars	>2 workshops	
	Publications	>6	
	Multimedia	1	
Phase 2 M12-24			
In this phase, which also marks the beginning of the Pilots, so a lot of the communication and dissemination efforts will focus on spreading information about those events. Moreover, the consortium will consolidate its efforts to take advantage of established links with other initiatives and to establish even more, as well as to present its research and product in events and exhibitions.	Website and social media updates	Size of online community >2500 Impressions/month >200	D5.1 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and activities, interim report(M18)
	General spreading	>6 Press releases >6 events (co)-organized by local authorities	
	Multimedia	2	
	Podcast	4 episodes	
	Blogs	>8 unique publications >6 different blogs	

	Newsletter	Quarterly issues >500 contact points	
	Workshops and Webinars	>4 workshops >6 webinars	
	Publications	>10	
	Presentations in conferences, events, exhibitions	>7 presentations >4 booths	
	Joint activities with sister/relevant projects	Link with >10 projects >10 initiatives >10 events >15 fairs	
Phase 3 M24-M36			
In the final phase of the project communications and dissemination efforts will be focused on spreading the projects results to identified audiences in order to increase the exploitation outcomes.	Website and social media updates	Size of online community >5000 Impressions/month >400	D5.2 Dissemination, communication and exploitation plan and activities, final report (M36)
	General spreading	>6 press releases >6 events (co)-organized by local authorities	
	Multimedia	1	
	Podcast	4 episodes	
	Blogs	>7 unique publications >2 different blogs	
	Newsletter	Quarterly issues >1000 contact points	
	Workshops and Webinars	>2 workshops >4 webinars	

	Publications	>8	
	Presentations in conferences, events, exhibitions	>6 presentations >4 booths	
	Joint activities with sister/relevant projects	>10 events >10 fairs	
	Final Event		

5.3. Dissemination Procedure

A step-by-step guide was created and shared with the consortium in order to ensure the efficient recording and monitoring of all communication and dissemination activities. Additionally to the dissemination procedures, a number of forms which are available to the consortium on the project's online repository were created. More specifically these are, a calendar of events and a dissemination registry form and an activity report form.

All of the above documents can be found in [Annex 3](#).

5.3.1. EU Acknowledgment

In every communication and dissemination material that is circulated and/or presented, the EU flag and the following disclaimer should be displayed in a clear and visible manner.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 14: EU Acknowledgment

Figure 15: EU Acknowledgment Example

5.3.2. Monitoring and recording

The monitoring and recording of dissemination and communication goals will be performed through tracking the specific KPIs which have been set in the GA. These are listed in the table below:

Table 8: Monitoring and Recording

Action	KPI
Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unique visitors M12 >1200 • Unique visitors M36 >3200
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Community >5000 • Impressions/month >400
e-Newsletter	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 9 released • >1000 contact points
Joint activities with relevant initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fairs to participate >25 • Relevant initiatives to establish links >15 • Co-organized events >20
Blogs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Publications/contributions >15 • No of different blogs >8
Printed Material	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard copies (i.e. brochures, flyers) >1500 In an effort to save paper this number might be amended. • Roll-up banners >6
Multimedia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Videos and interviews • Podcast • >4500 views
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >12 Journal Publications • >17 presentations in conferences • >12 Technical Publications • >8 participation in industrial exhibitions
Workshops & Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >8 Workshops • >70 participants per event (on top of consortium members) • >10 webinars
General spreading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • >15 press releases • >12 events (co)-organized by local authorities • People per event >150 (on average)

6. Exploitation Plan

6.1. Exploitation strategy

There are five main aspects to CiROCCO Exploitation strategy: commercial, scientific, social, capacity enhancement and policy outreach. Each of these facets plays a role in successful advancement of the CiROCCO results. The commercial aspect focuses on the development of viable business models and commercialization opportunities. This involves identifying potential markets, establishing partnerships with relevant industries, and devising strategies to generate revenue from the project's outcomes. The scientific and technological aspect focuses on contribution to cutting-edge research and technological advancements. The social aspect involves understanding the impact of the CiROCCO project on society and stakeholders. It entails engaging with local communities, addressing social concerns, and promoting inclusivity and diversity throughout the project's lifespan. Capacity enhancement aims to strengthen the skills and expertise of the individuals involved in the CiROCCO project. This involves providing training opportunities, fostering knowledge sharing and building human resources to ensure the project's sustainability and long-term success. The policy outreach aspect focuses on engaging with policymakers, regulatory bodies, and governmental institutions. By advocating for supportive policies and regulations, CiROCCO aims to create an enabling environment for its activities and to align its goals with broader societal objectives. By integrating and effectively managing these five aspects, CiROCCO Exploitation strategy aims to maximize the positive impact of the project, foster innovation and drive meaningful change in the targeted domains.

❖ Commercialisation

Four cross sectoral business models will be developed aiming to showcase the sustainability of the developed system. CiROCCO will use appropriate modelling tools such as the Business Model Canvas or the Lean Canvas to develop and select the appropriate business model(s), involving industrialists, research centres, and users to ensure the sustainability of the systems developed, with the goal of incentivising, acquiring, and retaining profitable customers and subsequent commercial growth. A decrease of 60% the total price per monitoring station is expected. Through the strategic selection of the consortium members, which constitute a representative value chain of actors, encompassing academic and research technology organisations, along with complementary skills obtained from pioneer SMEs and public organisations CiROCCO will result in concrete and sustainable business plans adopted to the actual needs and outputs from the pilots. CiROCCO aims towards the development of cross sectorial business models that support the sustainability of the installed equipment and further development in additional desert regions in Europe. This is supported by the commercialisation of the equipment and most importantly by a series of data processing technologies.

❖ Scientific and Technological advancement

CiROCCO consortium partners are committed to use the Open Research Europe scholarly fully open-access publishing service for Horizon Europe to enable rapid publication times and publication outputs that support research integrity, reproducibility, transparency and enable open science practices. CiROCCO will develop a network of in-situ sensors, which will be able to gather information for variables like air temperature, sand temperature, humidity, solar radiation, etc. For direct integration and exploitation of the derived data, the consortium will ensure that the metadata will be compliant with ISO 19157, QualityML and follow the recommendations of IPCC (Intergovernmental Panel on

Climate Change). This will result in the alignment and low effort integration with the current recommendations of the in-situ component of Copernicus, the GEOSS portal as well as ESA's guidelines. Moreover, the collected in-situ data will enhance the modelling and applications of other core Copernicus services, like the Copernicus Emergency Management Service (EMS), where the under-sampled desert areas are commonly affected by natural or manmade disasters and the lack of information leads to low quality products. Finally, considering the lack of in-situ data in deserts, the strategic network of CiROCCO can also assist on the Scientific Calibration and Validation (CAL/VAL) plans of specific satellite missions like the Aeolus, or even enhance the information of the current pseudo invariant calibration sites (PICS). Active engagement of citizens will improve science literacy and build expertise among civil society, better access and understand scientific information.

❖ **Social and environmental benefits**

CiROCCO aims to increase the decision-making capacity for future missions and climate change priorities by providing data from unrepresented areas, mainly desert regions. The developed services will have a direct impact towards the Green Deal priorities towards Zero pollution. CiROCCO aims to increase the precision of developed models by 10% and offer dedicated services to tackle climate change adaptation and mitigation planning. Through co-design and participative engagement methods, the real-world needs of the users, their requirements and any limitations they may experience to feed into technology and service design will be identified, so that these and associated future business model(s) meet real needs of hard-to-reach areas.

❖ **Capacity building**

CiROCCO has a great and innovative technological and scientific work to be exploitable, but also has a social exploitation aspect of major importance. CiROCCO's pilots reach out to society as a whole, as one of the objectives is to provide capacity building actions to the pilot areas. Thus, by enhancing the skills, capabilities and knowledge of local key players (stakeholders, communities, authorities and decision-policy makers, researchers and citizens), sets the proper conditions to ensure the longevity of the solutions provided by the project even after its lifecycle. CiROCCO will train and educate local communities to increase awareness for the project, involve more stakeholders to collaborate towards sustainability while having the minimum environmental impact on the pilot areas. Proper communication and dissemination using every available channel will contribute to visibility, outreach and subsequently impact of the provided solutions.

❖ **Policy outreach**

The pilots and the project results act as powerful tools for policy support and decision-making instruments and authorities, to the benefit of the society in the local and wider scales. The exploitation of products is expected by the authorities responsible for climate change, environmental management and conditions, health and air quality issues.

Business Objective (BO)

BO.1: To install and operate in-situ, low-cost, stand-alone, electronic sensing nodes in close collaboration with post project operating entities, having a real interest from local communities, including the commercial sector, offering a clear sustainability and commercialisation path beyond the project's duration.

The goal is to develop an economically and technically sustainable sensor network, composed of a distributed, cost-effective electronic sensing node, having a direct impact on the current and future activities of research centres, industry and public authorities. Commercialisation services will be developed to financially leverage the value of the collected data and ensure the funding needed for sharing with the research community. They include the development of Renewable Energy Systems (RES) planning services, Health Air Quality early warning system, modelling of Greenhouse Gases (GHGs) and Particles Emissions and, Ecosystem Management services. In addition, the access to data is provided with multiple sources (e.g., within few minutes with satellite communication), allowing the development of additional business models. Data fusion services are provided through a Big Data platform (INTRA's Streamhandler Platform), further supporting the commercialisation path of the datasets and the expansion of the system to additional desert areas, as well as different hard-to-reach areas.

KPI BO1.1: To develop services on top of the collected data, promoting the interoperability and commercialisation of the datasets: ≥ 4 services to be developed.

KPI BO1.2: Development of additional business models during project implementation: > 4 business models developed.

KPI BO1.3: To offer a clear sustainability plan allowing the expansion of the system after the project's implementation: a 5year sustainability plan to be produced and constantly updated during the project.

6.2. Joint Exploitation strategy

To orientate the outcomes from CiROCCO towards viable commercial solutions and assets, the consortium will adopt a focused commercialisation strategy with measurable outcomes by embedding commercial best practice into the project's lifecycle. Commercialisation will focus on delivering solutions that have a clear market opportunity that can be proven and validated through the pilots with key commercial stakeholders and in close collaboration with public authorities. The completed business models and marketing plan (deliverable D5.3) will aim to outline viable and commercially relevant solutions, assets and services from the project by taking a broad cross-consortium perspective, with credibility built on a foundation of embracing industry best practice for bringing new products to market. With the objective of achieving sustainability, continuity, and eventually prepare the ground for market entry for the project's results, the consortium has drafted and agreed upon its initial exploitation intentions. The plan consists of 3 phases:

Figure 16: CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline

Phase I (M01-18) setting the necessary conditions for the business plan;
 Phase II (M19-36) that coins the exploitation, sustainability and go to market strategy, and
 Phase III (starting at the end of the project) featuring the sustainability plan for the uninterrupted operation of the system and the commercialisation roadmap.

6.3. Key Exploitable Results

The consortium partners have decided to take a multi-level approach towards managing the knowledge produced, where the respective knowledge producer holds the rights to the knowledge and shares the software and hardware implementation with the rest of the consortium.

❖ CiROCCO Key Exploitable Results

The initial exploitation intentions towards the CiROCCO KERs are presented in Figure 17, which will be further refined and finalised during the project’s duration.

CiROCCO Key Exploitable Results	Owner(s)	Type	Licensing	Time to market
Low-cost, stand-alone electronic sensing nodes	EBOS	Product	Commercial	2y after project
Real-time access to data from hard-to-reach areas	ASTRO	Service	Commercial	1y after project
Data fusion service between high- & low-end sensors	NOA	Service	Open/Commercial	1y after project
Data fusion between EO and in-situ measurements	ICCS/NOA	Service	Open-source	6m after project
Big data services through the StreamHandler platform	INTRA	Service	Commercial	3m after project
Renewable energy systems planning	NOA	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Air quality early warning system for human health	UCY/NOA	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Land use and ecosystem management	INO/VSUME	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project
Modelling of GHGs and particles emissions	CSIC	Demonstrators	Open/Commercial	6m after project

Figure 17: CiROCCO exploitation plan and timeline

All KERs are planned to reach TRL8 by the end of the project; this means that the consortium partners who will commercialise the KERs after the project’s completion, requires minimal effort, in terms of technical work for progressing the solution to TRL9 and offer it with Europe and beyond as a commercial offering. Four business plans will be developed with products and services defined in deliverable D5.3 due in M11.

❖ Datasets

Partners have submitted a preliminary list of datasets for exploitation during and after the project, some of which will be made publicly available through GEOSS. A more detailed summary including the management of all data will be presented

Table 9: Exploitation summary for datasets created during CiROCCO

DATASET	FOR MAT	PARTNER	STORAGE	OPEN/ PROTECTED	EXPLOITATION MODE
Solar energy monitoring and forecasting	netcdf/mat/csv	NOA (SOLEA)	cloud	Open source during the project	Commercial provision. Support the distributed solar plants for production management, energy market operations optimization, maintenance efficient planning and early warning, energy security.
WRF -DUST	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide Information to about the prevailing air quality
WRF-DUST-Assimilated	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide improved quality Information to about the prevailing air quality
Data and metadata for the parametrization and results for the CiROCCO sensor-systems, with emphasis on PM measurements	csv	IERSD (APCG)	Cloud/ Zenodo	Open source after the project	Will support the research and sensor community to guide QAQC processes applied to commercial and under-development systems
Solar energy monitoring and forecasting	netcdf/mat/csv	NOA (SOLEA)	cloud	Open source during the project	Commercial provision. Support the distributed solar plants for production management, energy market operations optimization, maintenance efficient planning and early warning, energy security.
WRF -DUST	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide Information to about the prevailing air quality
WRF-DUST-Assimilated	netCDF	NOA (REACT)	CiROCCO system	open	Provide improved quality Information to about the prevailing air quality
Data and metadata for the parametrization and results for the	csv	IERSD (APCG)	Cloud /Zenodo	Open source after	Will support the research and sensor community to guide QAQC processes applied to commercial and under-development systems

DATASET	FOR MAT	PARTNE R	STORAGE	OPEN/ PROTEC TED	EXPLOITATION MODE
CiROCCO sensor-systems, with emphasis on PM measurements				the project	
Desert Dust Storm (DDS) Events Data	.csv	UCY	UCY	Open Source	The DDS Events Data can be used to better forecast future dust storms, helping to protect and prepare communities. End users benefit from improved forecasting accuracy and subsequent early warning alerts.
Early Warning System User Engagement Data	.xlsx	UCY	UCY	Open Source	User engagement data can be analysed to identify areas for improvement in the early warning system, enhancing the user experience and ensuring maximum impact. End users benefit from a system that is constantly improved and updated based on user feedback.
Sensors' readings	TBD	EBOS	CiROCCO data storage space	Open Source	EBOS does not plan to exploit the datasets at this stage
Land use / Land cover map	GeoTIFF	INO	VŠUME server, Data integration and management platform	Open source	further research/development
Ecological vulnerability map	GEOTIFF	INO	VŠUME server	Protect ed	further research/development, internal use
Long term ecological management study	PDF	INO	Zenodo	Open source	further research/development
Short term wild fire risk map	GEOTIFF	INO	VŠUME server, StreamHandler Platform	Open source	Public use, comercial, further research

DATASET	FOR MAT	PARTNE R	STORAGE	OPEN/ PROTEC TED	EXPLOITATION MODE
Short term drought risk map	GEOT iff	INO	VŠUME server, StreamHan dler Platform	Open source	Public use, comercial, further research
Database Inventory of Meteorological and Air Quality Data, monitoring and alerting tools and models for historical, current and future analysis of DDS exposure	.csv	UCY: Development and design MOL: Data provider , design	ICCS	Open Access	Future application in other Municipalities and Communities (inform the public, especially the vulnerable population groups for the air quality of their region). Measurements of the Air Quality Monitoring Network will be enriched at the local level.

In order to support the culture of sharing the knowledge and contribute to the wider community, partners will make individual efforts to contribute to creating CiROCCO dissemination material, outlined in the table below.

Table 10: Summary of dissemination material efforts by partners

Type of publication	Partners efforts to contribute
Peer reviewed articles	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, EBOS, NOA (SOLEA, REACT, APCG)
Research assessment/study	UCY, INTRA, INO, EBOS
Poster	ICCS, UCY, INO, NOA (REACT)
Product brochures	NOA (SOLEA)
Blog posts	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, NOA (SOLEA)
Project brochures/leaflets	ICCS, UCY, INTRA, EBOS
Infographics	ICCS, INO
Other diss&comm material	ICCS, INO, MOL, EBOS, NOA (APCG)

❖ Publicly available e-Trainings/Courses

All online tutorials/trainings/courses prepared by the CiROCCO project through its capacity building activities will be made publicly available through the project's website and will be posted in a public service, i.e., presentations will be published in SlideShare, whereas videos will be available through the CiROCCO YouTube channel and on Google podcasts app. These will be all licensed via a Creative Commons license (likely "CC BY") to maximise reuse and share of the knowledge and target increased involvement.

6.4. Individual Exploitation Plans

The CiROCCO consortium comprises of 12 organisations from 4 EU members, 1 Associated country and 2 non-EU associated countries that together form a complete group uniting the necessary expertise, skills, interdisciplinary knowledge and resources to constitute a representative value chain of actors (Figure 3.4), capable of achieving the demanding project goals. The consortium is multidisciplinary, encompassing 5 major Academic and Research Technology Organisations, along with complementary skills obtained from 3 pioneer SMEs, 1 Industrial Partner and 3 Public Organisations, to help achieve the ambitious goals of the CiROCCO project. Following are their individual exploitation plans, based on which further exploitation activities will be based.

6.4.1. Research Institutes and academic organisations

❖ ICCS

ICCS is a very experienced coordinating partner, with more than 80 successful projects coordination in H2020 and FP7. ICCS will ensure the strong coordination needed for such a big action involving a wide range of partners with different profiles and needs. It will lead the activities of the project regarding: (i) the system architecture design and technical specifications (ii) development of the algorithms running on the edge devices and the integration with the StreamHandler Platform, (iii) the technology validation and overall assessment of technologies as well as the replication guidelines. In addition, ICCS will handle the purchasing of all the equipment used in the sites ensuring the best possible prices of consumables and equipment. ICCS has experience in maintaining sensor networks gained from previous projects and ensure the post project sustainability of the installed equipment.

ICCS	800+ EMPLOYEES
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
ICCS exploitation targets include the production of research results, knowledge dissemination and pursuing the potential of a spin-off company to exploit established experience in developed solutions (in-situ monitoring of under-sampled desert areas, sensor networks, data fusion between EO and in-situ measurements, etc.). The above goals may be achieved through collaborating with other RTOs, non-profit organisations but also industrial partners. This collaboration acts as an enabler for exploitation opportunities both at a scientific level and at an R&D level.	
Expected Impact	
CiROCCO will support exploitation opportunities at two different levels:	
(i) <u>At a scientific level</u> , it will acquire in depth knowledge with respect to in-situ monitoring of environmental parameters in under-sampled areas, as well as enhance visibility through collaborating with strategic industrial players of the consortium thus adding an application-oriented direction in its activities.	
(ii) <u>At an R&D level</u> , the gain of experience and increased reputation in the field of sensor networks and solutions development to enhance monitoring of environmental parameters in under-sampled desert areas through CiROCCO will enable successful participations of ICCS in future related R&D projects.	

❖ NOA

NOA's role in CiROCCO is four-fold: 1) Exploiting its radiation and energy expertise in developing solar atlas, nowcasting and forecasting, and its previous experience in Egypt with regards to dust and energy

related collaborations, as well applications development (Solea), NOA will carry out solar related measurements and facilitate interaction with local partners. 2) Exploiting its weathered experience in in-situ measurements (APCG) and its state-of-the-art approach of scientifically fool-proofing lowcost networks for PM monitoring, NOA will be responsible for all QA/QC procedures of dust measurements across the pilots in close collaboration with the local partners. 3) NOA will handle the satellite remote sensing aspects regarding estimation of the dust optical depth (DOD) utilising the MIDAS and LIVAS in-house DOD datasets that will be also evaluated versus the lowcost sensors. Further, NOA will advance dust numerical simulations via data assimilation techniques in the pilot areas. 4) NOA will utilise its multi-faceted involvement in the GEO ecosystem to disseminate the project's results and pursue linkages with ongoing GEO activities, especially in the in-situ, remote environments and climate change themes. In terms of exploitation intensions, NOA (through Solea) will pursue the extension of the existing collaboration with the Egyptian New and Renewable Energy Authority and the Ministry of Electricity and Renewable Energy as well as explore commercialisation of the produced technical developments. The scientific results are of great interest both for IERSD and IAASARS groups and will reinforce their expertise in Mediterranean aerosol science opening opportunities for further scientific exploitation and enhancement as partners in relevant R&D projects.

NOA	300+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>Basic research is at the forefront of NOA's enduring scientific legacy; it is carried out by the three NOA institutes specializing in different scientific fields: (a) the Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications and Remote Sensing (IAASARS), specializing in the fields of astronomy, astrophysics, space science and remote sensing; (b) the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) specializing in the fields of air quality, environmental monitoring, meteorology, climate and climate change; and (c) the Geodynamic Institute (GI) specializing in physics of the Earth's interior and Earth surface deformation monitoring using remote sensing methods, in seismology, geophysics, volcanology, satellite geodesy and marine seismology. In order to support both basic and applied research, NOA promotes consistently the development of innovative facilities in support of research activities carried out by all its institutes; it currently operates more than 550 land-based measurement stations covering the entire Greek territory, which are equipped with antennae and satellite signal receivers so that they can access numerous satellites for acquiring high-fidelity data. IERSD/SOLEA deals inter alia with renewable energy sources (RES) research and development in terms of planning, management, exploitation and penetration into society. The RES market includes producers, electricity handling entities and decision makers. IERSD/APCG is involved in innovative technologies for air quality monitoring that rely on sensor technology. The relevant IERSD initiatives provide solutions in the framework of Atmospheric Sciences, Air Quality (AQ) Management, Exposure Science, and Citizen Science. The salient R&D focus that distinguishes IERSD in the field of sensor based AQ measurement is the rigorous calibration regimen followed for all operating and new sensor systems, which assures system reliability and data quality. Services are targeted at the academic/research sector, at public, regional and municipal Air Quality Management authorities, as well as at the private sector.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>Strengthening and empowering the RES expertise of IERSD. Gaining more expertise in operation and calibration protocols for sensor based AQ systems in remote and challenging environments. Strengthening the position of NOA as a research partner specializing in sensor-based, CS and IoT products. Utilization of the NOA brand for new networks with more/new public authorities & decision makers. Empowering in-situ EO in GEO.</p>	

New experience in RES production monitoring and forecasting in under-sampled regions affected by dust sources and transport. Energy potential estimation improvement by assimilating the in-situ information into the modelling processing chain.

Evaluation of the performance of PM sensors for dust measurements, for which data and applications are very sparse in the market. Accumulation of more experience in AQ QA/QC involving new IT approaches and training of new personnel. Capacity building to increase awareness, visibility and reach.

Establishment of IERSD in the Egyptian region as a key player for RES planning and management optimization. Promotion of a reinforcement method for renewable energy potential estimation and operational production handling by calibrating on-the-fly the modelling output with the in-situ data. Expanding the portfolio of sensor calibration applications to dust particles, which is a key component of PM10 – one of the priority pollutants –, provides opportunities in Southern Europe and the Eastern Mediterranean, where PM10 and dust are a chief concern for public health and the climate, due to their proximity to deserted areas or as receptors of LRT dust transport.

Market to remote, hard-to-reach- areas, new market segments

❖ CEDARE

CEDARE is an international inter-governmental non-profit organisation, accredited by the respective Arab and European Ministries of the Environment as well as the League of Arab States and the United Nations to conduct environmental and sustainable development studies and provide related services.

CEDARE	25+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>In the Arab region, environmental data is scattered between various organizations, regional and national research centres and statistical offices. The journey for data hunting is usually confusing, costly and time consuming. CEDARE's Sustainable Growth Programme (SGP) addresses new and emerging concepts related to environment and development for human well-being, with a focus on issues related to Sustainable Consumption and Production, Green Economy, and Green ICT. The Programme collaborates on global, regional and national efforts, addressing poverty alleviation, health, waste reduction (e-waste), green jobs, green ICT, pollution reduction, greenhouse gas emissions, sustainable consumption and production, and energy security. Together with its wide partner base from the international, regional and national community, the SGP implements projects, conducts research and studies, and provides training and knowledge dissemination.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>Through the CiROCCO project, CEDARE will conduct and coordinate the Egyptian pilot. CiROCCO will support exploitation opportunities at two different levels:</p> <p><u>At a policy level</u>, focusing on the active contribution in the formation of energy related policies and the subsequent market uptake by setting up and disseminating a roadmap for implementations exploiting the synergy of Earth-Observations with ground-truth sensors.</p> <p><u>At an R&D level</u> CEDARE will also use its network to provide valuable input regarding end-users' needs, being involved in the co-design and co-development procedures of the project and provide input and feedback for the development of the CiROCCO system and services.</p>	

❖ UCY

UCY will conduct and coordinate the Cypriot pilot, focusing on the robust and accurate early warning system for DDS events, by undertaking the training of local personnel in the management and maintenance of the monitoring stations, as well as participate in the set-up of the early warning

system, and will be involved in organising dissemination activities of the project results. UCY will also validate existing meteorological models for DDS forecasting with the availability of new data source.

University of Cyprus, Laboratory - Isle of Excellence of Environmental Fluid Mechanics	1553+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>The Environmental Fluid Mechanics (EFM) Laboratory, recognised as an Isle of Excellence, is a research laboratory of the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering (CEE) at the University of Cyprus (UCy). The EFM Lab facilities support both research projects and undergraduate teaching in Environmental Fluid Mechanics. The lab is equipped with a wide range of experimental arrangements for investigating fluid flow phenomena in environmental and industrial applications, such as urban air pollution dispersion, turbulence modelling, channel flows, buoyancy-driven flows and gravity currents, building ventilation, wind engineering, and coastal flows.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>The participation of the laboratory in the CIROCCO project will enhance:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The capacity to attract or be involved in new European research projects related to the interaction between Desert Dust Storms and Climate Change, Human Health, Socioeconomic aspects. 2. Its collaboration and partnership network at European level. 3. Its access to or capacity to develop of novel and operational models and methodology for assessing the personal exposure to DDS and related health threats. 4. Gaining experience to provide consulting services to public bodies on DDS adaptation measures. <p>As part of the CiROCCO project, forecasting models for Desert Dust Storms are being improved, new data collection technologies are being used, and a comprehensive early warning system is being created. Access to these tools will enable the EFM lab group to provide consulting services to public bodies on DDS adaptation measures.</p> <p>By implementing an early warning dissemination system that is tailored to local areas, more local authorities or government departments are likely to be interested in utilizing this know-how.</p>	

❖ CSIC

CSIC is Spain's largest public research institution, attached to the Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness, and plays a key role in scientific and technological policy in Spain and worldwide.

CSIC	N/A
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>Through the EEZA research group, CSIC will leverage its 75 years+ of expertise in the biodiversity and desertification research in arid zones, by conduct and coordinate the Spanish pilot, focusing on the formation and transformation processes of spatial and temporal variability of biogenic and non-biogenic aerosol sources and sinks.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>Through monitoring parameters and variables to prepare local to global models of GHGs and particles emissions, CSIC will supervise the smooth operation of the project's sensors in two selected dryland sites and will contribute to the design of the project's contingency plans.</p> <p>From the exploitation side, CSIC expects to advance knowledge in the Mediterranean drylands in</p>	

- (1) Vulnerability as hotspot of GHGs and particles emissions
- (2) CO₂ and CH₄ fluxes
- (3) Atmospheric boundary layer and particle fluxes; and
- (4) Groundwater quality associated to atmospheric chemistry.

6.4.2. Industrial Organisations and Small Medium Enterprises

❖ EBOS

EBOS technical role in the project, given its 18 years+ of expertise as a software powerhouse includes the acquisition of the pilot requirements and specifications from the pilot executors and translate those requirements into technical specifications of the technology to be developed within the project, as well as, to lead the pilots' work package and specifically the scene set-up, benchmarking definition, operational management and DevOps task. EBOS will be responsible to develop the low-cost, in-situ electronic sensing nodes that will be used in the high-density sensor network aiming to enhance the in-situ measurement resolution in hard-to-reach areas. Apart from designing and maintaining the project's website, EBOS will also leverage its wide experience in the market, to contribute to the elaboration of CiROCCO dissemination and sustainability plans and present project's results to key associations through its membership (e.g., DAIRO, AIOTI, NESSI).

eBOS Technologies Ltd	70+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and a short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
eBOS Technologies Ltd has more than 18 years of experience as a software powerhouse however, dedicated personnel within the company have more than 10 years of experience in the development of electronic sensing nodes. The company now operates in the FinTech & RegTech market for its software solution. Within the last 2 years, it expanded into the hardware electronics sector with multiple R&D projects, both internally and EU funded.	
Expected Impact	
EBOS plans to use the pre-existing version of the stand-alone, sensing system and the knowledge to design such systems to expand their activities by introducing themselves in the electronic testing and sensing equipment.	
CiROCCO project will support this strategic move of the company by allowing the further development and characterization of the system specifications. CiROCCO will test the system in real-life conditions providing valuable information for the evolution of the system to high quality and higher TRLs.	
The strategic decision of the company to move into this market will of course attract new and more customers from a completely different sector.	

❖ INTRA

INTRA participates in the project as an experienced integrator of digital manufacturing and IoT systems, which a very strong track record of participation in tens of successful EC co-funded projects, as well as commercial deployments for manufacturing enterprises.

Netcompany-Intrasoft	3200+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	

Netcompany-Intrasoft (previously known as INTRASOFT International) was established in 1996 and quickly became a European leader in IT solutions and services with strong international presence. Its headquarters reside in Luxembourg and has development centres and operational branches in Greece at Athens, Thessaloniki, and Patras but also in Belgium, Romania, Denmark and further three countries. There are also offices in the USA, the UK, Cyprus, Bulgaria and the United Arab Emirates. Netcompany-Intrasoft has proven expertise in conceptual system architecture and system design, development of advanced enterprise microservices applications and CI/CD solutions, information portal management and project management. Emphasis is always put on developing applications that are modular, secure, and reliable and importantly, on offering innovative and added-value solutions that meet each customer's individual business needs.

Not surprisingly, Netcompany-Intrasoft holds an outstanding record of +500 organisations (including EU institutions and agencies, national government organisations, public agencies, financial institutions, telecommunication organisations and private enterprises) in +70 countries worldwide having chosen and trust the company's solutions and services to fulfil their business needs.

Expected Impact

As of November 2021, Netcompany-Intrasoft is a member of the Netcompany Group, the fastest growing and most successful IT services company in the Nordics, owing technology experience and industry-specific knowledge. As part of the Netcompany Group, Netcompany-Intrasoft continues to look for opportunities to capitalise on existing technical and business expertise and expand into new or adjacent sectors. By filtering industry trends and identifying emerging key enabling technologies, the company infiltrates its portfolio of products and solutions with these technologies to differentiate from the competition.

The participation of Netcompany-Intrasoft in the CiROCCO project is motivated by the possibility to showcase its cloud-based real-time data exchange platform and further develop Streamhandler's capabilities for IoT applications.

Netcompany-Intrasoft is also interested in the commercial exploitation of Streamhandler by building applications for land use and environmental monitoring and attracting additional users from other industries.

Additionally, Netcompany-Intrasoft is interested in exploiting knowledge gained in further research activities other than those covered by the CiROCCO project and acquiring a competitive advantage by enhancing and underpinning the company's position in Europe's research and innovation ecosystem.

❖ INO

INO will lead exploitation activities in order to ensure the sustainability of system developed as well as be in charge of developing coherent business model(s) involving industrialists, research centres, and end users. INO will also contribute to development and deployment of the Serbian pilot activities, as well as be actively involved in communication and dissemination of the project activities, results and achievements.

INSENS

6 employees

Brief intro to your organization and short analysis of the market in which your organization is currently operating

InoSens is an innovation-driven boutique consultancy specialising in delivering innovative, scalable technology solutions and business services for diverse European value chains. InoSens is Serbia's most successful SME in terms of the number of EU funded projects.

Expected Impact

INO will enlarge its know-how in the areas of commercialisation and business modelling for EO/in-situ monitoring applications and solutions at an EU level and will further develop its management and networking practices, allowing it to improve and expand its services portfolio.

INO will coordinate the data acquisition, processing and analysis from the meteorological and air quality sensor network. The data will be used for short term (24h) drought and wildfire condition assessment, public health risk alert system (based on measured inhalable particulate matter, daily situation reports relevant for the area of southern Banat region and the Belgrade metropolitan area, with more than 1.5 million inhabitants). In parallel, **INO** will conduct ecological modeling based on EO products, field surveys of changes in land degradation and evaluation of the different risk factors. **INO** will also prepare studies of long-term ecological management, risk avoidance and mitigation planning.

INO will capitalise on its strong existing position and business activities with strategic partners in this market, to improve its services portfolio and expand its contact base for the development of international collaborations, especially within the public sector.

❖ ASTRO

Founded in 2014, Astrocast is a leading global nanosatellite IoT network operator that offers a Cost-effective, Bidirectional and Comprehensive Satellite IoT Service to tackle global connectivity challenges in remote areas for industries such as Maritime, Agriculture & Livestock, Environmental & Utilities, Land Transport, Mining, Oil & Gas, and other IoT industrial applications. The Astrocast network enables companies to monitor, track, and communicate with remote assets from anywhere in the world, and is the only New Space IoT LEO network with commercial access to L-band through a strategic alliance with Thuraya. In partnership with Airbus, CEA/LETI and ESA, Astrocast developed the Astronode S, an ultra-low power and miniaturised module compatible with inexpensive L-band patch antennas. Astrocast is a public company listed on Euronext Growth Oslo.

ASTROCAST	35+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and a short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
ASTRO is a leading global nanosatellite IoT company based in Switzerland. Working toward completing 100 satellites constellation by 2024, ASTRO currently serves its customers globally with 10 nanosatellites and is planning to launch 10 more by the end of 2022.	
Expected Impact	
During the CiROCCO project, ASTRO will leverage its knowledge and equipment on satellite connectivity for IoT applications (low energy, short messages, small antenna size) to gather communication from any type of sensors or data logger in the field (remote area). By defining the data flow architecture, data formats, communication protocols and services, ASTRO will also develop the communication gateways to interconnect the wireless sensing nodes with the edge/cloud. From the exploitation side, ASTRO expects to advance knowledge and reinforce understanding in project's advances, extending the company's R&D activities.	

6.4.3. Public Organisations

❖ DIMOS

DIMOS will act supportively and as advisory body in the impact assessment process, as its feedback during the definition of the end-users needs, as well as during the Cypriot pilot execution, will provide valuable insights for enhancing the user-friendliness of the designed tools and the sustainability of project results. Also, DIMOS will widely use and promote the early warning dissemination system for DDS events, that will eventually positively impact its citizens and enrich its provided services.

Idalion Municipality	24 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>DIMOS (named Idalion) is an independent municipality of Cyprus (public administration authority) that is located in the southern part of Nicosia province. It is the modern city of the ancient city (Kingdom) of Idalion that was founded by the hero of the Trojan war, Halkanora.</p> <p>The Municipality of Idalion is active in the field of providing services to its citizens. The main responsibilities of the Municipality are the construction, maintenance and lighting of the streets, the collection, disposal and processing of garbage, the protection and improvement of the environment and the good appearance of the Municipality, the construction, improvement and maintenance of parks and green spaces and the protection of Public Health. The Municipality via the Municipal Council is empowered to promote, depending on its financial capabilities, several other areas and activities such as the arts, education, sports and social services.</p> <p>The services of the Municipality of Idalion today consist of the following departments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Office of the Mayor and Municipal Secretary. • Secretariat-Archive: This Department serves as the backbone for the Municipality. Assist Municipal Council. • Financial Department: Payroll preparation, Payment of creditors and other expenses. • Cultural Service: Organisation of cultural, artistic, social and other events of Municipality. • Health Service: Conduction of health inspections of food preparation and distribution premises, sampling of drinking water from the Municipality's water supply system and from water tanks, inspections of swimming pools and control of their water quality, informing citizens about various matters of health interest, insects (e.g. mosquitoes and flies) and rodents control, cleanliness of the Municipality, investigation of complaints of sanitary importance, protection of the Environment and Public Health etc. • Technical Services: Street/Road Network Planning, Zoning Studies, Complaints of a technical nature. • Employee Department: Implementing the specified personnel administration policies and procedures. 	
Expected Impact	
<p>Within CiROCCO project Idalion will provide guidance and expert advice on the design and attributes of the DDS early warning system and will provide feedback throughout the development process. Also, Idalion will support the impact assessment process and will provide valuable insights for enhancing the user-friendliness of the designed tools and the sustainability of project results. It is expected that the CiROCCO project results will help the Municipality to enhance its knowledge on the Environment and Municipal Health issues, focusing on the air quality.</p>	

In addition, the project will give the opportunity to the Municipality to promote the early warning dissemination system for DDS events, that will eventually positively impact its citizens and enrich its provided services. The results of the project will create a solid framework to strengthen the transformation of Idalion into a smart city, a fact that is currently a hot topic and priority of the municipal authority.

Development of a service through which the citizen will be informed about the air quality in the Municipality where he lives.

❖ MOL

MOL will actively contribute to the pilot in Cyprus and will provide consultation and input regarding the user experience, which will be integrated in the tools' development. MOL will also use the in-situ measurements to enrich its monitoring system and enhanced its provided services, while promoting the sound decision making in policy for the green transition, and take into consideration the results regarding transferability to similar areas in Cyprus and public information regarding the air quality over the island.

Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance	922 employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>The Department of Labour Inspection (DLI) of the Ministry of Labour and Social Insurance (MLSI-MOL) is the Competent Authority for the monitoring of various atmospheric pollutants, as well as for the assessment and management of air quality, in order to secure, as practically possible, the protection of the health and well-being of workers and citizens and the protection of the environment.</p> <p>The aforementioned measurements are carried out using nine Stations, fully equipped with automatic real time instruments measuring the following pollutants: Nitric Oxide, Nitrogen Dioxide and Nitrogen Oxides (NO, NO₂ and NO_x), Ozone (O₃), Sulphur Dioxide (SO₂), Carbon Monoxide (CO), Suspended Particles (PM-Particulate Matter) (dust) and Benzene (C₆H₆). It is noted that, Air Quality Reference Laboratory, as well as the Air Quality Monitoring Stations Network (AQMN), are accredited by the Cyprus Organization for the Promotion of Quality (CYS-CYSAB) according to the Standard CYS EN ISO/IEC 17025:2017. In addition, the most important meteorological parameters are monitored such as Wind Direction, Wind Speed, Ambient Temperature, Relative Humidity, Atmospheric Pressure and Solar Radiation.</p> <p>The results of the measurements as well as other relevant information are presented on-line, through the specialized website www.airquality.gov.cy. Since 2017 the Department of Labour Inspection operates a mobile phone application with the aim to directly inform the public, especially the vulnerable population groups, the employees and other interested people. Through this application, the visitor has access to the information for the air quality, in real time, based on the different colors of pollution levels on Cyprus map, as well as based on the concentrations of pollutants per station.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air Quality Monitoring in small communities (Communities / Municipalities) using sensors in conjunction with Air Quality Monitoring Network measurements funded by the Municipalities themselves. • Placement of screens in Municipalities / Communities to inform citizens on Air Quality in real time as well as other relevant information. 	

- Informing the Local Authorities / Citizens, by DLI-MOL Officers, with lectures / presentations on air quality issues and the main problems presented in Cyprus (dust / ozone).
- With the pilot study in the Municipality of Idalion (DIMOS) and the possible future application in other Municipalities and Communities, the measurements of the Air Quality Monitoring Network will be enriched at the local level but with less accurate measurements coming from sensors.

❖ VSUME

The Public Company for Forest Management “Vojvodinašume” is a private entity in charge of the management over protected area of Deliblato Sands Special Nature Reserve (35.000ha), where CiROCCO Pilot 3 will be located.

Public company Vojvodinašume	1852+ employees
Brief intro to the organization and short analysis of the market in which it is currently operating	
<p>The Public Company for Forest Management “Vojvodinašume” is a private entity in charge of the management of the over protected area of Deliblato Sands Special Nature Reserve (35.000ha), where CiROCCO Pilot 3 will be located. The company is organised into three organisational levels:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Company Directorate 2. Sections of the Company- forest holdings and the sections of the Company “Vojvodinašume – Lovoturs” Novi Sad – Petrovaradin and „Vojvodinašume-Turist“ Petrovaradin. 3. Work units – forest administration and other work units. <p>The Company Directorate performs strategic, development and coordination activities and supervision of the work of sections of the Company. Organisational structure of the Directorate consists of sectors. Forest holdings are established on the level of forestland areas and their organisational structure consists of services. Forest administrations are basic units for planning and organisation of forest management activities. Apart from forest holdings such as: “Sremska Mitrovica” Sremska Mitrovica, “Sombor” Sombor, “Novi Sad” Novi Sad and “Banat” Pančevo, the Company also consists of the sections of the Company specialised in hunting and breeding game “Vojvodinašume – Lovoturs” Petrovaradin and „Vojvodinašume-Turist“ Travel Agency is a specialised agency, tour operator.</p> <p>Public Company “Vojvodinašume” sells wood products mainly on the national market and minor part on international market.</p>	
Expected Impact	
<p>During CiROCCO, VSUME will conduct and coordinate the Serbian pilot, focusing on the land, forest and protected habitat management and tourism development, supporting the pilot’s and project’s outreach activities, including setting all the necessary monitoring devices across the designated areas and engage with the relevant local end-users.</p> <p>VSUME will demonstrate the capabilities of the developed tools, aiming at indicating fragility to land degradation processes, assessing the impact of air pollution, monitoring the ecological balance and stability, and facilitate decision making to safeguard sensitive areas.</p> <p>Improved monitoring of the protected areas in terms of air quality and pollution levels might contribute to growth in tourist visits to Deliblato Sands. Experience of devices usability could/might be applicable to other areas (protected areas and forests out of protected areas) managed by</p>	

Vojvodinašume, but final decision would be made after evaluation of effectiveness of CiROCCO project devices

7. Strategy for the Management of Intellectual Property

In conformance with the rules for participation of current European Programs, a minimum set of basic principles concerning ownership of knowledge and access rights have been fixed and detailed with the signature of a Consortium Agreement (CA) before the start of the project, which regulates rights and obligations by all partners and will be further updated during the project execution. The IPR provisions distinguish between 2 basic types: • Background knowledge: Access rights necessary for the execution of the project will be granted on a royalty free basis. • Foreground knowledge: Intellectual property protection of foreground, i.e., the knowledge developed in the project and its applications will be filled, owned and funded by the partner(s) that developed the particular results. Each partner shall inform the Project Coordinator and the project partners 4 weeks in advance of the filing of a patent application. Subject to the provisions of the EU Grant Agreement and the CA any owner of any result shall be free to use such results and to move it to the market. In case of joint ownership, each owner shall be free to use such results in its own organisation but adhere to the CA and exploitation strategy with regards to commercialisation.

Relevant to knowledge management, CiROCCO will employ the following strategy:

❖ • Intra-Consortium Knowledge Management:

- 1) Technical and scientific progress: create documents and place them in a document repository to ensure that every partner has access to them.
- 2) Exploitation perspectives: the WP exploitation leader will structure, and map required knowledge and extra-knowledge needed to enhance exploitation (i.e., patents, technology transfer agreements, potential users, other projects) and propose an exploitation strategy.

❖ • Extra-Consortium Knowledge Management:

Knowledge management will take place through dissemination to maximise the impact of the work done within the project. The exploitation leader (INO) will be in charge of collecting and proposing to the consortium all matters referring to the results for dissemination and will monitor the productivity of the project in terms of knowledge publications (scientific papers, posters, etc.).

8. Conclusion

This deliverable is an initial plan on the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities that the consortium aims to follow in order to maximize awareness, visibility, engagement and commercialization.

CiROCCO is an innovative and ambitious project which aims to create environmental, societal, economic and scientific impact through technology advancement, useful synergies with relevant

initiatives and policy making influences. Therefore, it is important to have a clear map of actions to follow and a comprehensive set of tools that help steer the consortium's efforts in this direction.

It is also important to monitor and evaluate all Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities with the help of clear-cut KPIs to ensure that the aforementioned impacts are maximized.

The plan that has been presented is dynamic in nature and all necessary changes will be adopted in order to ensure that it best serves the project's goals in each step of its lifecycle.

9. References

1. Drew, C. (2023). Laswell's Model of Communication-5 Key Features. HelpfulProfessor.org; online
2. HTML 5.2-W3C Recommendation (2017);online
3. CSS3 Tutorial;online
4. JavaScript;online

Annex 2 Individual Communication and Dissemination plan

CiR CCO
Individual Communication and Dissemination Plan

PARTNER NAME

DATE

CONTACT PERSON

1) Participation in Events
Participation to events (Conferences, Seminars, Public Events, Exhibitions)
Planned activities
Period: 2023 - End of the project

No.	Name of the event (which event)	Date (when)	Place (where)	What to present
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

2) Publications
Publications (journal, conference proceedings, magazines)
Planned activities
Period: 2023 - End of the project

No.	Targeted journals / Conferences	Place (where)	Topic related to the industrial sector	CiRer's interest to be involved in the activities (using ONLY the organization)
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

Funded by the European Union

CiR CCO

3) Joint Activities
Established activities with relevant partners
Planned activities
Period: 2023 - End of the project

No.	Name of sister project	Type of activity	Date	Place
1.				
2.				
3.				
4.				

4) Communication activities
Website, Social Media, e-Newsletter and email Campaigns, Press Releases, Blogs, Printed Material, Multimedia
Planned activities
Period: 2023 - End of the project

No.	Activity	Date	What to present
1.			
2.			
3.			
4.			

Other Comments

Funded by the European Union

Figure 20: Individual Communication and Dissemination plans

Annex 3 Dissemination Procedure

Dissemination Procedure

Description and Purpose

The participation of any partner in an event, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of CiROCCO or the performance of any other dissemination activity related to the project has to be approved beforehand by the CiROCCO Consortium.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally to:

- Produce high quality CiROCCO publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed.

The WP5 leader (INO) and the T5.1 leader are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. All partners are called to contribute efficiently on the dissemination of the project.

Step by Step Procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the CiROCCO project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify the the T5.1 leader (Dimitris Maragkos: dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr) at least 45 working days in advance about the intention to participate on a dissemination activity, sharing a) the details of the activity (date of event, name of journal, title of activity, audience, etc.), b) their specific role in it (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, etc.) and c) a short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to CiROCCO (See Relevant information Table below);

STEP 2: Register the activity in the applicable tab on the [Dissemination Register](#), specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file;

STEP 3: If applicable, store the relevant material (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) in the WP5 Dissemination folder on Teams, under the related sub-folder (Events, Publications or Other);

STEP 4: the T5.1 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments which should be sent to the WP5 leader within 30 days; no response is considered as an approval;

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or REA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 21: Dissemination Procedures

Dissemination Activity Report

The dissemination activities report should be filled in by the leading partner of every realised dissemination activity. The purpose of this report is to provide the necessary information to the T5.1 leader and WPS Leader for publishing the activity to the CiROCCO website and for reporting to the European Commission.

There are three report tables in this document:

- A report in case of an event (e.g., project event, conference, exhibition, etc.);
- A report in case of a scientific publication (e.g., conference papers, journals/magazines, book chapter, etc.);
- A report in case of any other dissemination activity related to CiROCCO.

Please fill in the applicable report table and send the document to the T5.1 leader (Dimitris Maragkos, ICCS: dimitris.maragkos@iccs.gr) along with any presented material (full paper, article, poster, presentation etc.), also indicating whether the WPS team has the permission to publicise this material (on the website, social media, etc.).

In case of Events (i.e. Project Events, Conference Presentations, Exhibitions etc.)	
Title of event / place & date of realisation:	
Type of Event:	Conference, Workshop, technical meeting etc.
Title of presentation:	
Type of presentation:	poster presentation, paper presentation, demo presentation, oral presentation...
Relevance to CiROCCO:	Please specify: WPx work, concept description etc.
Author(s)/ Presenter(s):	Name (company)
Other activities (if any)	i.e. distribution of promotional material, bilateral discussions etc.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or ICA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1

Figure 22: Activity Report

Date	Title of Event	Type of Event	Location	Website	Info/Key dates	Other
20-21 March 2023	CIRCCO KAM	Kick-off	Athens			

Figure 23: Calendar of Events

Date	Title	Authors	Journal/Conference	Location	Type of activity	Progress status	Status	Social on Twitter	Impact
Year 1 (M1 - M12) March 2023 - February 2024	Solar Photovoltaic Hotspot Inspection Using Unmanned Aerial Vehicle Thermal Images at a Solar Field in South India	Prudhviraj U. Kulkarni P. Sankaranarayanan C. Ramaprasad P.	MDPI Remote Sensing		Journal Publication	100%	Complete		
	Algorithms for Hyperparameter Tuning of LSTM for Time Series Forecasting	Dhruv H. Kulkarni P. Sankaranarayanan C. Ramaprasad P.	MDPI Remote Sensing		Journal Publication	100%	Complete		

Figure 24: Dissemination Registry

Annex 4 List of Conferences

CIROCCO Calendar of Events

File Edit View Insert Format Data Tools Extensions Help

100%

Date	Event	Location	Website	Important deadlines
2023				
	WMO Data Conference			
	UN Climate Change Conference			
	IEEE/ACM Open Science Conference			
	International Conference on Atmospheric Dust			
	IEEE International Instrumentation and Measurement Technology Conference			
	International Conference on Electronics			
	Communications and Control Engineering, Conference on Missions Monitoring			
	Evidence Based Policy Making in Europe Conference			
	IEEE Sensors Conference			
	EDU conference 2023			
	IEEE Transactions on Circuits & Systems			
	International Conference on Applied Meteorology and Climatology 2024			
	International Conference on Public Health 2023			
2024				
26-27 March 2024	International Conference on Electronic, Information and Industrial Engineering	Kviteseid, Norway	http://www.electrif.com/	February 16, 2024
14-15 April 2024	EDU general assembly 2024	Vienna, Austria (online)	https://meetingsorganizer.copernicus.org/AGU24/provisionalprogramme	September 13, 2023
26-23 May 2024	IEEE Instrumentation & Measurement	Glasgow, Scotland	https://im24.2024.ieee-ims.org/	September 22, 2023 (Special Session) November 24, 2023 (paper submission)
17-18 June 2024	INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY IN METEOROLOGICAL MATERIALS	Dresden, Germany	http://www.im2024.de/	the end of 2023

Figure 25: List of Conferences

Annex 5 List of Publications

Title of journal/Magazine	Website	Impact Factor	ISSN (Open Access/Not Open Access)	Description (scope and topics)
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/International-Journal-of-Applied-Earth-Observation-and-Geoinformation	7.62 (2022)	OA	The International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation publishes original papers that apply earth observation data to the inventory and management of natural resources and the environment.
Environmental Science and Pollution Research	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/Environmental-Science-and-Pollution-Research	4.18 (2022)	Hybrid	Environmental Science and Pollution Research (ESPR) serves the international community in all areas of Environmental Science and related subjects with emphasis on chemical compounds. It reports from a broad interdisciplinary subject. Apart from the primary sciences, contributions as research articles (short and full papers) and reviews, ESPR publishes news & views from research and technology, legislative and regulatory, hardware and software, education, business, institutions, organizations, conferences.
ISCC Instrumentation & Measurement Journal	https://www.iscc-journal.com/	1.54	OA	The ISCC Instrumentation & Measurement Magazine covers a wide variety of topics in instrumentation, measurement and systems that measure or monitor equipment or other systems. The magazine has the goal of providing readable introductions and overviews of technology in instrumentation and measurement (IM) to a wide engineering audience. It covers this through articles, feature columns, and departments. Its goal is to cross disciplines to encourage further research and development in IM.
Environmental Challenges	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/Environmental-Challenges	1.8	OA	Environmental Challenges, a companion journal of Journal of Environmental Management, is an international journal devoted to the publication of original research findings and review articles in new areas of environmental management and environmental science as a multi-disciplinary journal publishing high-quality and novel information.
Open Access Government	https://www.openaccessgovernment.org/		OA	Open Access Government is a digital publication that provides an in-depth perspective on his public policy areas from all around the world, including health and social care, COVID-19, research and innovation, technology, government, environment and energy.
One Earth	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/One-Earth	16.2	Supports OA	One Earth publishes significant original research that seeks to understand and address today's environmental grand challenges. The journal publishes across the full spectrum of global environmental change and sustainability science, providing a single platform to write research from the natural, social and applied sciences.
Atmospheric Environment	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/Atmospheric-Environment	6	Supports OA	Atmospheric Environment is the international journal for scientists in different disciplines related to atmospheric composition and its impacts.

Figure 26: List of Publications

Annex 6 Individual Exploitation Plan

A template was sent out to all partners to fill in.

[PARTNER NAME]	+ X EMPLOYEES
Brief intro to your organization and short analysis of the market in which your organization is currently operating	
[100 words max]	
Expected Impact	
Please answer the following. How will CiROCCO support:	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Evolution of your organization, and/ or expansion to new sectors of interest. > Growth and development of your products and services. > Reaching out to more/ new customers. 	

IP Rights

CiROCCO Partner	Background IPR / Project Contribution	Business Opportunity/ foreground

DATASETS

Dataset	Format	Responsible partner	Where the data will be stored	Opensource/ Protected	Exploitation Mode
[name of dataset]	[type of file format]	[partner]	[e.g., on which server or data archive]	[describe]	[desired exploitation of the dataset, how do the end users benefit]

PUBLICATIONS

[please check all the boxes that apply to your organisation's plans and possible contribution]

Peer reviewed articles	<input type="checkbox"/>
Research assessment/study	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poster	<input type="checkbox"/>
Product brochures	<input type="checkbox"/>

Blog posts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Project brochures/leaflets	<input type="checkbox"/>
Infographics	<input type="checkbox"/>
Other diss&comm material	<input type="checkbox"/>

Figure 27: Individual Exploitation Plan